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Tasks for landscaping residential areas and microdistricts

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Abstract: Socio-demographic factors have a great influence on the formation of the landscaping system in settlements and microdistricts: an increase in the number of the population of retirement age, increased activity in raising the younger generation, the development of contacts between different age groups (children, youth, adults, pensioners), taking into account such needs of the population as loneliness and information exchange, lack of time, and minimizing the radius of access to recreation areas.

Key words: Residential areas, microdistricts, landscaping,

INTRODUCTION

The development of a country is judged by the well-being of its villages and cities, the culturally well-organized landscapes, the smoothness and beauty of its roads and streets. In this regard, great work is being carried out in our country, which is becoming more beautiful day by day, under the personal initiative of our President Islam Karimov. An example of this is the reconstruction of all cities in our country, the large-scale construction of model housing in rural settlements, and the rapid implementation of similar major reforms. The need to organize the reconstruction of villages and cities, form their aesthetic appearance,

eliminate autonomous development, and integrate villages and cities, based on natural, functional requirements, while preserving natural resources and historical and cultural potential, while raising ecological, social and economic issues to a new, qualitative level, which is stabilized, balanced, and integrated, is being implemented by the state programmatically today.

The harmonious improvement of greening in our country, along with socio-economic issues, is unthinkable without the participation of highly qualified architects and designers. According to the data presented, the need for greening is evidence of the close connection of man with nature,

and nature is an integral part of it, and the environment is a leading tool in managing human emotional activity. The fate of our small planet is in the hands of people today. The number of huge industrial enterprises that emit waste is increasing year by year, millions of hectares of forests are disappearing from the face of the earth, causing an ecological crisis. Of course, this can lead to serious consequences. The leadership of our state, personally my esteemed President, is paying great attention to the environmental issues of our country, improving the greening of villages and cities. This should be understood as an effort to increase the well-being of our people and raise the status of the Motherland. The inclusion of the state program to improve the quality of training of landscaping designers and architects places a great responsibility on the staff of higher educational institutions and colleges. It can be said that the attitude towards landscaping in the districts of our regions is not entirely up to the required level. The daily growth of the population has led to a sharp decrease in arable land. Settlements have expanded in any direction without a plan or project. This has led to a sharp decrease in useful arable land. Today, the concept of "Sustainable Development" is being discussed. This

is a stable socio-economic development, which is considered a concept that leads society to continuous progress without violating its natural foundations. Sustainable development is a process that can only be achieved by a developed society, and now it is called the noosphere (the world created by human intelligence, as opposed to the product of primary nature). To ensure a sustainable life in our country, all sectors of development tools must be coordinated, including the architecture and design of greening, which should integrate cities and villages, reduce the differences between them, solve the problems of roads, which are one of the nodes of socio-economic development, within the framework of the planning structure, ensure the proportionality of residential areas and agricultural lands in the overall greening project, and pay great attention to the architectural, artistic forms and compositional, constructive structure of greening in the project.

The well-being, spiritual stability, environmental harmony, and comfort of living of the citizens of our country, which is embarking on a great path of development, are directly related to the beauty of the surrounding environment, and greening is indispensable in this.

All types of residential complexes or structures of the residential area of the city are formed in accordance with the principle of a tiered service system.

The first stage of providing services to the population is represented by institutions and enterprises, as well as buildings of daily needs. These are, as mentioned above, grocery stores, communal services, children's and physical education playgrounds, recreation areas for adults, parking lots near residential buildings, kindergartens and schools. This also includes a green area around a group of residential buildings or a garden of a residential group, including various structures and sites.

The second level of service to the population includes institutions and enterprises that have daily and periodic needs, including shops, canteens, household workshops, clinics, pharmacies, cultural and household service enterprises, green areas of microdistrict significance - a microdistrict park intended for recreation of the population. the entire population, including sports.

The third level of service includes enterprises and institutions, structures and devices that are used periodically and episodically, such as large stores (department stores, grocery stores), cafes, clubs, restaurants, hotels, cinemas and theaters, district clinics

and hospitals, museums. , a sports complex, garden or park in a residential area.

Residential area - the largest structural unit of the residential zone of small and medium-sized cities. For the structure of large cities, such a unit is a residential (planning) area consisting of several residential buildings.

The radius of development of a residential area is formed on the basis of pedestrian convenience to institutions and cultural and household service enterprises located at a distance of 1000-1500 m from the house. The population is usually 25-60 thousand people. and more depends on the number of storeys of the building. The choice of the most rational population for a residential area depends on the size of the city, the number of storeys of the building, natural conditions and landscape features of the territory.

The boundaries of settlements are the main streets of city and district significance, as well as large green spaces - parks, gardens, parks.

According to the general planning features of the residential area of the city, residential areas are formed in the following forms:

- groups of adjacent territories separated by highways and streets or green lines;

- groups separated from each other by natural water bodies, forests, cabbage soup, as well as highways and highways;

- separate territories separated from each other by natural barriers (hills, mountains, etc.).

Residential areas, as a rule, are divided into microdistricts - the main structural divisions of the residential area of the city.

A microdistrict is a residential complex that provides the most necessary needs of the population (education of the younger generation, cultural and economic and local services). It should be located no more than 500 m from residential buildings and residential areas of kindergartens, schools, dairy, dairy products, housing, housing and playgrounds. The service radius determines the population. With five-story buildings, this is 6-12 thousand people, with mixed-18-20 thousand people. (Providing 9 m² of living space per person).

Microdistricts become a single residential area, forming a system of specific enterprises and institutions for serving the population (stage 2). The number of microdistricts included in the residential area depends on local conditions and the general goals of urban planning. A residential area in a small and medium-sized city, the territory of which does not intersect

with the main street, cannot be divided into microdistricts.

The boundaries separating the territories of residential areas and microdistricts from city streets are called red lines. Buildings along the street are placed along the border located at a distance of at least 6 m from the red line and are called building lines.

Main part.

Issues of rational organization of housing are addressed at all stages of design, construction and operation. The pre-project period includes an analysis of the urban planning situation and local natural and landscape features.

Socio-demographic factors have a great influence on the formation of the landscaping system in settlements and microdistricts: an increase in the number of the population of retirement age, increased activity in raising the younger generation, the development of contacts between different age groups (children, youth, adults, pensioners), taking into account such needs of the population as loneliness and information exchange, lack of time, and minimizing the radius of access to recreation areas.

The landscaping system of settlements and microdistricts should be developed taking into account environmental factors and should contribute to improving the sanitary,

hygienic and aesthetic indicators of the environment and ensure:

- ensuring the biological stability and aesthetic value of existing and designed plantings, soil cover in conditions of high anthropogenic loads;

- creating normal conditions for aeration of the space, reducing noise levels, gas pollution, dust, ensuring compliance;

optimal mode of insulation of the territory;

- selection of a stable assortment of plants, creating a rational structure of plantings, eliminating negative effects on the human body.

The effectiveness of landscape organization of residential areas is of great importance. When developing design solutions at all stages of design, the following rules should be followed:

- compliance with the maximum preservation of existing landscape elements - plantings, reservoirs, relief forms, soil cover;

- development of a landscaping system and its planning elements, taking into account multi-purpose use;

- use of techniques that provide complex mechanization of work for the implementation of the project;

- widespread use of standard landscaping and landscaping elements.

The organization of the landscape of residential complexes is solved in an integral way from development. In

essence, this is a single process that takes into account a variety of architectural, planning, urban planning, engineering, agrotechnical and environmental factors. Developing a project for the organization of the landscape of microdistricts, groups of residential buildings and individual buildings is one of the main tasks of urban or rural development. Such a project should take into account the natural features of the area - the surrounding landscape, relief, reservoirs, vegetation as much as possible. At the stage of design and survey work, landscape engineers should carefully analyze the areas and territories of residential construction intended for improvement. It is of great importance to collect information on residential areas, the system of streets and highways, parking lots, walkways and pedestrian routes, the number of residents, their social composition, age structure.

At the stage of the detailed planning project, the issues of the landscaping system of the residential area are resolved, that is, the rational placement of all categories of plantings, depending on the specifics and characteristics of residential construction, the system of squares, streets, highways, public and shopping centers. At the same stage, it is necessary to implement a general

design decision on nature protection: maximum preservation of the relief, plantings and reservoirs; organic inclusion of natural elements in the overall architectural and planning solution. Such an approach can only be implemented with a thorough study of the natural conditions of the area and the direct participation of specialists.

The landscaping system of settlements consists of greening objects that differ in their functions. Its composition includes all main categories of plantings in the city, with the exception of plantings of urban significance.

All green areas are divided into three categories:

- general use - parks, gardens of residential estates, squares, alleys, green areas near public and administrative buildings, gardens in neighborhoods or gardens in groups of residential buildings, courtyards or green areas in residential buildings;

- limited use - green areas of schools, kindergartens, nurseries, clubs, cinemas, clinics, libraries, etc., residential areas, etc.

General requirements for the improvement of residential areas and microdistricts

The improvement of residential and microdistricts and microdistricts is determined by urban planning requirements.

Total height of the building, m, depending on the number of floors

4- multi-storey	18
5- multi-storey	20
6- multi-storey	25
7- multi-storey	29
8- q multi-storey	32
9- multi-storey	36
10- multi-storey	40

The width of the buildings and the distances between them are determined

By the height of the building located on the south side. In areas with little sun, tears can be increased, and in areas with a lot of sun, their decrease is allowed. The norms of sanitary gaps are given in table

1. Isolation of the greened residential area is of great importance.

Residential plots and gardens of residential groups should be a number of areas available for sunlight throughout the year.

At the same time, it is necessary to provide shading of individual areas in the hot summer. The desired effect can be obtained when planting trees with dense crowns or using various structures - canopies, walls, pergolas, etc. When designing the landscaping of a residential area, it is important to take into account its illumination and shading during the day, as well as in the hot season, in order to choose the right assortment of plants. For this purpose,

a schedule of insolation of the area is drawn up using special insolation lines (light planimeters). As an example, the universal insolation line developed by MLTIDA is given.

The most promising method for calculating the insolation of development on a computer. The calculation of direct solar radiation (insolation) is carried out on the basis of methodological recommendations for ensuring normative insolation in residential and public buildings and in the construction area (No. 13184, A 84). The thermal regime is determined by the total solar radiation and air temperature and is calculated by various methods [applying the duration of insolation to the plan, determining the amount of thermal energy according to tables, applying isolines with a multiple of 1000 kcal/ (m² - day)].

The wind regime is an important factor. In areas with a large number of them, windless, calm days should ensure ventilation of the area. This is achieved through a certain arrangement of buildings that takes into account the main directions of air flow. Usually, closed courtyards cause air stagnation. Houses located "in a row" are arranged linearly in the direction of air movement, on the contrary, creating favorable conditions for ventilation of the territory. It is

important to take into account the main direction of the wind in this area. Data on wind directions are obtained from weather stations: for these conditions, the so-called wind rose is taken into account. (According to weather stations, wind roses are measured at a height of 10-15 m, and the aeration construction mode is formed at a height of 2 m above the human habitation.)

In areas with strong winds, development should be compact, closed. To protect against wind, protective lines of seedlings, special house screens oriented on one side to the prevailing winds, can be used.

Figure 1 shows options for simultaneously protecting residential buildings from strong winds and highway noise. Such solutions help to optimize the hygiene regime in the living environment.

Economic requirements. The main economic indicator is population density. The size of the buildings, their capacity, number of floors, density of placement on the allocated area and the number of inhabitants are also of great importance. When developing a project for the improvement of a residential area, it is also necessary to calculate the individual elements of the territory - areas for various purposes, roads, planting areas. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the

number of people living in this microdistrict and the area of the territory occupied by construction.

Figure 1.1. The density of the population of a microdistrict is the number of people living in

1 hectare of residential area of the microdistrict.

Based on the housing norm of 9 m² per 1 person, the density of the housing stock is introduced, which is determined by the total number of living spaces per 1 hectare of residential area of the microdistrict. The higher the multi-storey buildings, the greater the living space in the microdistrict. For example, in a 5-story building, the area of the housing stock is 4800 m²/ha, and in a 9-story building - 6300 m²/ha. In mixed construction, the density of the housing stock can be increased to 6500-7500 m²/ha.

Knowing the density of the housing stock and the average rate of residence, it is possible to determine the population density of the microdistrict

$n = P / p$ people / hectare where p - population density; P - density of the

housing stock; p - average level of population of the point.,

Depending on the number of inhabitants, multi-storey buildings and the calculated density of the housing stock, the size of the microdistrict can vary within 10-25 hectares.

Having determined the approximate indicators of residential buildings - population density, building density and housing stock, it is possible to calculate the area of individual elements of the microdistrict. Table 8 shows the specific dimensions of individual elements of the territories per person and the area of green spaces, buildings and other improvements.

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